

Effect of Video Clips on the Letter Sound Recognition Skills of Pre-school Learners

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the effect of using video clips on the letter sound recognition skills of kindergarten learners. It subsequently assessed the impact of this intervention initiated by the researcher on the letter sound recognition skills of the research subjects. The research was carried out at Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The study involved 50 preschool learners, divided equally between section A (the control group) and section B (the experimental group). Both groups were homogeneous in terms of composition and academic performance. Subjects from both sections A and B were non-randomly assigned and participated in the study. The study adopted the new normal learning modality, a form of blended learning where modules were provided by the teacher online, adhering to Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) protocols. The researcher conducted follow-up sessions online to reinforce module content. Results indicated that the use of video clips had an impact on the letter sound recognition skills of preschool learners. Additionally, there was a significant difference in post-test scores between the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. video clips 2. letter sound 3. recognition skills

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1. Introduction

Pre-School learners are easily distracted, keen on independence and still developing self-regulation that the teacher cannot easily address the child in learning. It needs patience, kind, gentle personality and has a teaching style so that learners will hold their attention in the discussion. However, watching video clips is implemented to help child learn independently especially in letter sound. Instructional use of videos is undertaken in different ways and for different purposes. For instance, videos are used for teacher candidates to observe their classroom management skills by watching their own teaching process (Rosaen, Lundeberg, Cooper, Fritzen, Terpstra) and to identify educational strategies by observing their colleagues' educational experiences (Sherin Han). In learning any language, the most basic component to it is letters, and if one cannot recognize the letters, it will be challenging for young learners to venture into learning to recognize words, phrases and meanings (Waters, n.d.). Hayes (2016) even further supported the claim that the instruction of recognizing the letters upon sight is an important skill for young learners to have before embarking into a more chal-

lenging skills in language learning especially for reading. Both the Early Reading First and Reading First programs set explicit goals seeking to increase participants' letter knowledge and understanding of letter-sound correspondences. According to Kay videos are classified in different categories (such as: educational videos, video classes, e-lessons, screen captures, vodcasts (video podcast) and web broadcasts (webcast) based on their preparation, different presentation techniques and educational goals. While videos may consist of previews/short presentations about a specific topic or include information, they may also record the whole class hour (Kay). Videos create opportunities for in-depth learning by presenting various learning data together such as images, movement and sound. This allows learning to take place at individual paces and ensures control over the re-

ception of information (Greenberg and Zanetis). When education that is supported by videos is compared with face-to-face education, it is argued that videos are more effective since they support the process. In a study conducted in two different classes, Hakkarainen, Saarelainen and Ruokamo compared face-to-face teaching and teaching through online videos and identified that more meaningful learning took place in the classes taught via videos, and positive feelings emerged towards the learning process. In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, students watching video clips in order to learn the letter recognition and how it will affect them. The researcher being a teacher in the above educational institution would like to explore other dimensions in solving the merging problem. Hence, this is action research.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study makes use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 50 pre-school learners – 25 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 25 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from

sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25 –item test that will eventually determine the reading comprehension skills of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the reading comprehension skills of

the kindergarten learners. On the hand, post-test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the level of the reading

comprehension skills of the kindergarten learners, the following continuum was used based on DepEd rating system.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts

of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the level of the reading

comprehension skills of the grade two learners in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of interaction on the comprehension skills of the grade two learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the pre-school learners. The controlled group got the mean of 14.23 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 15.40 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group Pre-test	25	14.23	57.20	Beginning
Experimental Group Pre-test	25	15.40	61.6	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Waters who said that In learning any language, the most basic component to it is letters, and if one cannot recognize the letters, it will be challenging for young learners to venture into learning to recognize words, phrases and meanings and the most basic component to it is letters, and if one cannot recognize the letters, it will be challenging for

young learners to venture into learning to recognize words, phrases and meanings (Waters, n.d.) In learning any language, the most basic component to it is letters, and if one cannot recognize the letters, it will be challenging for young learners to venture into learning to recognize words, phrases and meanings (Waters, n.d.). Hayes (2016) even further supported the claim that the instruction of recognizing the letters upon sight is an important skill for young learners to have before embarking into a more challenging skills in language learning especially for reading.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group Post-test	25	20.47	81.88	Developing
Experimental Group Post-test	25	21.74	86.96	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the pre-school learners. The controlled group got the mean of 20.47 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 21.74 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.34 from a mean rating of 14.40 to 21.47. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Kay who cited that Both the Early Reading First and Reading First programs set explicit goals seeking to increase participants' letter knowledge and understanding of letter-sound correspondences. According to Kay videos are classified in different categories (such as: educational

videos, video classes, e-lessons, screen captures, vodcasts (video podcast) and web broadcasts (webcast) based on their preparation, different presentation techniques and educational goals. While videos may consist of previews/short presentations about a specific topic or include information, they may also record the whole class hour (Kay). Education that is supported by videos is compared with face-to-face education; it is argued that videos are more effective since they support the process. In a study conducted in two different classes, Hakkarainen, Saarelainen and Ruokamo compared face-to-face teaching and teaching through online videos and identified that more meaningful learning took place in the classes taught via videos, and positive feelings emerged towards the learning process.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	37	-5.57	.0431	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.57 with a p-value of .0431 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the pre-school learners. This implies that the used video clips on the letter sound recognition skills in teaching pre-school learners have contributed the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the pre-school learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Rasi and Poikela, (2016). who said that Video is being used in a variety of ways to support various pedagogical strategies successfully. By

no means a comprehensive list, within just the context of problem-based learning, video clips can be used to present a problem to students to trigger problem-solving; to provide information around the topic; or to present solutions to the problem at the end of the process (Rasi and Poikela, 2016). The use of videos for educational purposes has cognitive and effective impact. In this context, he argues that use of videos in the classroom environment will have potential effects such as: arousing student interest, facilitating student concentration, providing learning practices for highly relaxed students with low levels of interest, developing imagination, supporting creativity and increasing comprehension Berk.

Table 4 highlights the test of video clips on the letter sound recognition skills approach on the historical appreciation skills of pre-school

learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.441 which signifies large effect. This implies that Instructional use of videos is undertaken in dif-

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Kindergarten Pupils

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
50	-4.45	0.441	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

ferent ways and for different purposes. For instance, videos are used for teacher candidates to observe their classroom management skills by watching their own teaching process (Rosaen, Lundeberg, Cooper, Fritzen, Terpstra [27]) and to identify educational strategies by

observing their colleagues' educational experiences (Sherin Han). In video practices, the learner masters the real objects and movement sequences by observation and the videos provide opportunities for in-depth learning (Zhang, Zhou, Briggs and Nunamaker).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. *Findings*—This study sought to determine the effect of effect of video clips on the letter sound recognition skills of pre-school learners. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact groups of learners. This study will be conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 50 pre-school learners – 25 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 25 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of video clips on the letter sound recognition skills of pre-school learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between

the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the pre-school learners in both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Advanced level.

4.3. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching pre-school teachers should use video clips on the letter sound recognition skills as a strategy that use of videos shows that use of video or multimedia materials in education increases learning. If learners take part in the learning process by experiencing the unfolding of the lesson, then he will appreciate the concept, thus, he is learning. Teaching with videos is recognized as a powerful communications medium. The school heads should promote the use of video clips on the letter sound recognition skills as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed in the study

that it is effective especially on subjects that are narrative in nature and are not interesting to learners. A school policy about the utilization of video clips on the letter sound recognition skills can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using play as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of video clips on the letter sound recognition skills as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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